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INNOVATIVE TEACHING METHODS: ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES

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Abstract. In the period of technological developments, significant changes are occurring related to new scientific discoveries, informatization, globalization, development of robotics and artificial intelligence. The use of innovative technologies and programs is widely used not only in the field of IT, but also in the education system. The purpose of this article is to summarize the use of innovative teaching methods, to study innovation in teaching, the importance of improving the quality of education.

Keywords: innovative methods, pedagogical skills, technology, education, modern information, innovative ideas, digital generation, pedagogy.

O'QITISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI: AFZALLIKLARI VA KAMCHILIKARI.

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Annotatsiya. Texnologik taraqqiyot davrida yangi ilmiy kashfiyotlar, axborotlashtirish, globallashtirish, robototexnika va sun'iy intellektning rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq jiddiy o'zgarishlar ro'y bermoqda. Innovatsion texnologiyalar va dasturlardan foydalanish nafaqat IT sohasida, balki ta'lim tizimida ham keng qo'llanilmoqda. Maqolaning maqsadi o'qitishning innovatsion usullaridan foydalanishni umumlashtirish, o'qitishdagi innovatsiyalarni, ta'lim sifatini oshirishning ahamiyatini o'rganishdan iborat.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsion usullar, pedagogik mahorat, texnologiya, ta'lim, zamonaviy axborot, innovatsion g'oyalar, raqamli avlod, pedagogika.

As in every other sphere, education is developing rapidly and opening new opportunities for schoolchildren. Nowadays, many European educational institutions are using unique methods and learning programs in their daily activities. With the help of various multimedia resources, there are more

possibilities to make students be interested in a certain subject or demonstrate aspects of it to them in more detail. Innovative teaching method refers not only to the technological part used in class. A psychological approach and an analysis of children's behavior and perception of the information they receive are also important for discussing this work. Indeed, innovative teaching is the process of proactively introducing new teaching strategies and methods into the classroom. The purpose of introducing these new teaching strategies and methods is to improve academic outcomes and address real problems to promote equitable learning. Innovation – is a new idea, method or device [1]; methods of teaching that involve new ways of “teacher -student” interaction, a certain innovation in practical activity in the process of mastering educational materials. It helps to learners not only get a lot of knowledge, but also improve their intellectual, creative skills and create something new independently, work with different sources of information. [2] Devices such as laptop, iPad, and smartphones can be used to help students learn in new and innovative ways. For example, teachers can create digital flashcards for students to review or have them complete online quizzes. As Plato wrote, “our need will be our creator” or as we say today “necessity is the mother of invention”. Introducing innovative teaching strategies into the classroom may have been a nice academic practice conducted by a few bold educators previously, but these strategies are becoming more commonplace today as school look to make up for learning loss and our new reality [3].

The acceleration of innovative teaching in education happened during the pandemic, and it continues to improve. Moreover, lockdown with COVID-19 made teachers develop different creative ideas to keep students engaged in their classroom. While most of classes were online, students had to get accustomed to this type of learning.

What they used and still use are:

- Virtual online meetings
- Informal discussion on social media
- Online groups
- Autonomous learning

We learn through social interaction, so online or face to face, social interactions are what helps us build our behavioral and effective systems. While autonomous learning helps students grow, social interactions helps students push their boundaries. [3] In addition, if we compare to the past where teaching was based on teacher's interest and style, today the education sector is seen focusing on the interest and curiosity of students. Education specialists plan to adopt more and more new methods of teaching and learning and customize them according to the convenience of learners. As evolution in education takes place, the education providers look forward to most trending and attractive ways of teaching. To cope with the advancing technology it is important to blend the method of teaching and learning with digital technical tools and services.

The pros and cons of innovative teaching methods are like a both side of coin. Of course, we know that, for this form of learning and teaching we need to update techniques. It is about a few disadvantages of modern education:

- Digital learning is expensive
- Lack of social interaction
- Inexperience increases among teachers

There are many pros and cons of modern education trends in terms of its expense because the cost of connectivity is high but it should be made affordable for maximum learners to get its benefit in full. And also, it has affected social interaction among students a lot. They feel less motivated and lack peer interaction, sometimes they feel bored as there is not much communication between teachers.

In modern life, there is a need to keep up with modern technologies in every field, they are also used in the field of education. However, these innovative teaching methods sometimes take teacher's place, so it has an impact on the learning potential of teachers.

As any situation should be discussed from two points of view, the modern education trends' pros and cons both should be debated to know the weightage of each. This emerging trend is moving at a faster pace all over the world and it is time to realize the practical approach and feasibility and make learning more productive. To sum up, it is understood that the advantages outweigh the disadvantages because the shortcomings can be easily overcome with some restrictions and planning by understanding the effective use and importance of innovations in academic development [4].

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